

A demarcation of risk categories for invasion risk assessments using the *Harmonia*⁺ protocol

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Introduction

Motivation

D'hondt *et al.* (2015) presented a template for assessing the risk of introduced (non-native) organisms that could potentially become invasive, referred to as the *Harmonia*⁺ protocol. The protocol allows for an assessor's answers to be translated into numeric scores, from the level of individual questions to summaries of the organism's overall risk. Scores always lie within the [0,1] interval.

This quantification allows species to be ranked relative to one another, yet does not allow for classifying species into groups, since no risk categories have been defined. This was a deliberate omission, since the demarcation of such categories is ultimately subjective, depending on what a user considers a 'low' or 'high' risk.

Indeed, the main purpose of the *Harmonia*⁺ protocol is to provide the community with a flexible tool for risk assessment, and it is still highly recommended to customize settings to the user's specific needs.

Nonetheless, users have expressed a desire for such categories, often by setting thresholds among categories themselves. Therefore, we develop a suggestion for a default demarcation of risk categories in this memo, which is available on Zenodo ([link](#)).

(Note: a former version of this memo, dated 2015-12-07, was available with the authors but had remained unpublished.)

Key references

- Article: D'hondt B, Vanderhoeven S, Roelandt S *et al.* (2015) *Harmonia*⁺ and *Pandora*⁺: risk screening tools for potentially invasive plants, animals and their pathogens. *Biological Invasions* 17: 1869-1883. doi:10.1007/s10530-015-0843-1 ([link](#)).
- Online protocol: landing page ([link](#)) and online form ([link](#)).

Risk categories

As explained in D'hondt *et al.* (2015), the limited number of possible answers per question, in combination with the mathematical operations performed on them, means that (1) both module and above-module scores can only take any of a *discrete set of output values*, and (2) these values are *non-uniformly distributed*. These distributions are shown in Fig. 4 of the article.

Here, we develop a **three-level categorization** and a **five-level categorization**, with the following risk classes.

- Three-level: low, medium, high.
- Five-level: very low, low, medium, high, very high.

We develop threshold values so that each class has an **equal size**, i.e. the naive probability for a species to end up in each class is the same among classes. Thus, generally, one in three species ends up in the ‘low’ class, and one in three in the ‘high’ class, with the three-level categorization. For the five-level categorization, this would be one fifth of the species per class. See below for alternative approaches (unequal-sized classes).

Method

Approach

To define the threshold values, simulations are performed: answers to the questions from the protocol are given **randomly**, and scores are calculated (cf. D’hondt *et al.* 2015: Fig. 4). For this memo, we ran the protocol 10.000 times.

We then identified the output scores whose *cumulative percentiles* are *closest to .33 and .66* in the case of the three-level categorization, and *closest to .20, .40, .60 and .80* in the case of the five-level categorization. This approach is visualized in the figures from the **annex**. The selected scores are understood as the bin’s upper boundaries.

The only exception is the categorization for the *overall Impact* when calculated as the maximum over different impact scores (five modules). Doing so skews its distribution heavily to the right, particularly because of the *Other impacts* module which has only one question. Simulations show that this might transform a *high Environmental impact* into a *low overall Impact*. Instead of dividing the *overall Impact* into equal groups, it is therefore better to apply the logic of the maximum also to the risk classes: **the overall Impact risk class is equated with the highest risk class from the five impact modules (*)**.

The simulations are performed with R, and Rmd scripts with code are attached to this memo. These should allow users to perform simulations and define threshold values themselves if they wish to customize the protocol’s settings.

Protocol choices

We include two popular uses of the protocol. Please refer to D’hondt *et al.* (2015: Fig. 1) for full understanding.

Default: full protocol, default settings

- All questions are included (25 questions).
- All questions have equal weights.
- All modules are included (Introduction, Establishment, Spread, Environmental impact, Plant impact, Animal impact, Human impact, Other impact).
- All modules have equal weights in above-module operations.
- Default operations are used (arithmetic mean [within modules], geometric mean [for Exposure], maximum [for Impacts], product [for Risk]).

Alternative: environmental impacts only, default settings

As above, but with a restricted set of modules (reflecting the user’s primary interest in environmental targets).

- The following modules are included: Introduction, Establishment, Spread, Environmental impact.

Results

The suggested thresholds are shown in the tables below.

Default: full protocol, default settings

Table 1: thresholds for the **Introduction**, **Establishment** and **Spread** scores, and the **Exposure** score, in **three** classes. Full protocol with default settings.

Module	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH
Introduction	≤ 0.3333333	≤ 0.5	≤ 1.0
Establishment	≤ 0.25	≤ 0.5	≤ 1.0
Spread	≤ 0.375	≤ 0.625	≤ 1.0
Exposure	≤ 0.3605624	≤ 0.5263633	≤ 1.0

Table 2: thresholds for the modules on impacts on **Environmental**, **Plant**, **Animal**, **Human** and **Other** targets, and the overall **Impacts** score, in **three** classes. Full protocol with default settings.

Module	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH
Environmental	≤ 0.4166667	≤ 0.55	≤ 1.0
Plants	≤ 0.4166667	≤ 0.5625	≤ 1.0
Animals	≤ 0.375	≤ 0.5833333	≤ 1.0
Humans	≤ 0.375	≤ 0.5833333	≤ 1.0
Other	≤ 0.25	≤ 0.5	≤ 1.0
Impacts score	(highest from the above, see text (*))		

Table 3: thresholds for the overall **Risk** score, in **three** classes. Full protocol with default settings.

Module	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH
Risk	≤ 0.2593568	≤ 0.40625	≤ 1.0

Table 4: thresholds for the **Introduction**, **Establishment** and **Spread** scores, and the **Exposure** score, in **five** classes. Full protocol with default settings.

Module	VERY LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	VERY HIGH
Introduction	≤ 0.1666667	≤ 0.3333333	≤ 0.5	≤ 0.6666667	≤ 1.0
Establishment	≤ 0	≤ 0.25	≤ 0.5	≤ 0.75	≤ 1.0
Spread	≤ 0.25	≤ 0.375	≤ 0.5	≤ 0.75	≤ 1.0

Module	VERY LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	VERY HIGH
Exposure	≤ 0	≤ 0.3968503	≤ 0.4782328	≤ 0.5928156	≤ 1.0

Table 5: thresholds for the modules on impacts on **Environmental, Plant, Animal, Human** and **Other** targets, and the overall **Impacts** score, in **five** classes. Full protocol with default settings.

Module	VERY LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	VERY HIGH
Environmental	≤ 0.35	≤ 0.45	≤ 0.5416667	≤ 0.625	≤ 1.0
Plants	≤ 0.3333333	≤ 0.4375	≤ 0.55	≤ 0.625	≤ 1.0
Animals	≤ 0.25	≤ 0.4166667	≤ 0.5	≤ 0.6666667	≤ 1.0
Humans	≤ 0.25	≤ 0.4166667	≤ 0.5	≤ 0.6666667	≤ 1.0
Other	≤ 0	≤ 0.25	≤ 0.5	≤ 0.75	≤ 1.0
Impacts score	(see text (*))				

Table 6: thresholds for the overall **Risk** score, in **five** classes. Full protocol with default settings.

Module	VERY LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	VERY HIGH
Risk	≤ 0	≤ 0.2939021	≤ 0.375	≤ 0.4724704	≤ 1.0

Alternative: environmental impacts only, default settings

If, everything else being equal, only **Environmental** impacts have been assessed from among the impact modules, then all thresholds are as above apart from the overall **Impacts** score and overall **Risk** score. The suggested thresholds are shown below.

Table 7: thresholds for the overall **Impacts** score and overall **Risk** score, when only **Environmental** impacts were scored, in **three** classes.

Module	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH
Impacts score	≤ 0.4166667	≤ 0.55	≤ 1.0
Risk	≤ 0.1455967	≤ 0.2620741	≤ 1.0

Table 8: thresholds for the overall **Impacts** score and overall **Risk** score, when only **Environmental** impacts were scored, in **five** classes.

Module	VERY LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	VERY HIGH
Impacts score	≤ 0.35	≤ 0.45	≤ 0.5416667	≤ 0.625	≤ 1.0
Risk	≤ 0	≤ 0.1719754	≤ 0.2371262	≤ 0.3147964	≤ 1.0

Discussion

Other approaches

The ideal (but utopic) way

Although the division into three or five equal groups provides a convenient way of classifying species, this not necessarily reflects how invasion risks are truly perceived. Under the premise that impactful species are a small minority from the wider set of species (cf. the tens rule in invasion ecology), categories of unequal sizes might in fact be more accurate. Indeed, as was acknowledged by D'hondt *et al.* (2015), the left-skewed distribution of Risk scores accords well with that understanding.

However, in this case the exact, absolute threshold among high- and lower-risk species can only be set by calibration, by labeling particular species as high-risk apart from scoring. This could theoretically be achieved if a high number of assessments become available.

Thresholds .33 and .66

A forward, but very simplistic option is to use score values of .33 and .66 (3-level) or .20 to .80 (5-level) as a choice of thresholds. We thus warn that the size of (or the probability for a species to end up in) these classes is not straightforward.

To provide an example, below are the sizes of the groups in a three-level categorization (thus using .33 and .66 as thresholds), for the case when all modules are included, and for the case when only environmental impacts are assessed. **This demonstrates that species will almost never be qualified as high risk but in the most extreme cases.** This could well be accurate (in line with the previous paragraph), but the user should consider if such conservatism fits the purpose of the assessment.

The figures from the annex can be used to estimate the consequences of applying particular thresholds.

Table 9: group size for **Exposure**, overall **Impacts** and overall **Risk** scores if .33 and .66 are taken as thresholds (three-level categorization). Full protocol with default settings.

Module	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH
Exposure	28.14 %	60.22 %	11.64 %
Impacts	0.09 %	28.31 %	71.6 %
Risk	49.56 %	47.4 %	3.04 %

Table 10: group size for overall **Impacts** and overall **Risk** scores if .33 and .66 are taken as thresholds (three-level categorization). Only **Environmental** impacts assessed.

Module	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH
Impacts	18.23 %	68.43 %	13.34 %
Risk	83.31 %	16.54 %	0.15 %

Annex

The figures show the cumulative frequency of the possible output values for each of the modules. The horizontal lines refer to the equal-sized groups for each risk category (three or five in number). The arrows point towards the suggested thresholds (i.e. the scores that are nearest to the horizontal lines).

3-level categorization

5-level categorization

Environmental impact module - cumulative frequency of possible values, arrows point at suggested thresholds

Plant impact module - cumulative frequency of possible values, arrows point at suggested thresholds

Animal impact module - cumulative frequency of possible values, arrows point at suggested thresholds

Human impact module - cumulative frequency of possible values, arrows point at suggested thresholds

Other impact module - cumulative frequency of possible values, arrows point at suggested thresholds

Risk - cumulative frequency of possible values, arrows point at suggested thresholds

